

Study of mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} with some antibiotics and vitamin- B_1 drugs. Kinetics of electrode reactions

Firoj Khan and Farid Khan*

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 9 November 2006, revised 3 May 2007, accepted 11 May 2007

Abstract : Polarographic technique was used to study the ternary complexes of Zn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and vitamin- B_1 as secondary ligand at pH 7.30 ± 0.01 ($I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$) at $25^\circ C$. Zn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with stability constants trend neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V and penicillin-G. Kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ), diffusion coefficient (D) and rate constant (k) have also been determined.

Keywords : Antibiotics, vitamin- B_1 , mixed ligand complexes, electrode reaction.

A systematic survey on the formation of ternary complexes and kinetic parameters of Zn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and vitamin- B_1 as secondary ligand is tacking. In the present communication, we have presented our study on the same polarographically.

Results and discussion

A well defined two-electron quasireversible wave of Zn^{II} was observed at pH 7.30 ± 0.01 and ($I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$) (maintained althrough the experiments) at 298 K. The nature of current-voltage curves of Zn-complexes with antibiotics and vitamin- B_1 was also quasireversible.

The metal and ligands were taken in the ratio of 1 : 40 : 40 and current-voltage curves were taken at different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift in $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH 7.10–8.50, but, pH 7.30, the pH of human blood, was selected for the work.

Zn-neomycin-vitamin- B_1 system : In this system, the concentration of neomycin varied from 0.5 to 30 mM at 0.025 and 0.050 M fixed concentration of vitamin- B_1 at 0.5 mM of Zn at pH 7.30 at 298 K. The $E_{1/2}$ became more negative when vitamin- B_1 was added to the [Zn-neomycin] system indicating ternary complex formation. Similar complex formation was also observed in case of other antibiotics¹ (Table 1). The kinetic parameters were

calculated as before. The parameter Z that measures the degree of irreversibility was calculated by the method given in the literature². The values of stability constants are given in Table 2.

The value of $\log K_m$ which compares the stability of binary and ternary complexes, is given by the following equation²

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - \frac{1}{2} [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

The values of $\log K_m$ are -1.005, -0.735, -0.725 -0.525 and -0.040 for [Zn-neomycin-vitamin- B_1], [Zn-chlortetracycline-vitamin- B_1], [Zn-oxytetracyclin-vitamin- B_1], [Zn-tetracycline-vitamin- B_1] and [Zn-penicillin-G-vitamin- B_1] systems respectively, showed that binary complexes are more stable than their ternary complexes. Since 1 : 2 complex is not formed in case of [Zn-penicillin-V] therefore, $\log K_m$ was not calculated for this system.

The trend of stability constants of complexes was neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V < penicillin-G. This order of stability constants supported the order of pK values of tetracycline and also the stability constants of these drugs with their metal complexes as reported earlier². In all the above systems, [Zn-neomycin-vitamin- B_1] formed the complexes of lowest stability, which might be due to the considerable steric hindrance present in neomycin and Zn. In case of penicillin-V and penicillin-G, the ring nitrogen and O of the carboxylic group may take part in

Note

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics and F_{ij} [X, Y] values^a of [Zn-neomycin-vitamin-B₁] system
 $Zn^{II} = 0.50$ mM, pH = 7.30 ± 0.0, $\mu = 1.0$ M NaClO₄, $T = 298$ K, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.40$ mg^{2/3}s⁻¹

[Neo.] × 10 ³	[Vitamin-B ₁] = 0.025 M				[Vitamin-B ₁] = 0.050 M							
	$\log I_m/I_c$	$E_{1/2} - V$ vs SCE	F_{00} [X, Y]	F_{10} [X, Y]	F_{20} [X, Y]	F_{30} [X, Y]	$\log I_m/I_c$	$E_{1/2} - V$ vs SCE	F_{00} [X, Y]	F_{10} [X, Y]	F_{20} [X, Y]	F_{30} [X, Y]
			× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁷	× 10 ⁹	× 10 ⁹			× 10 ⁷	× 10 ⁷	× 10 ⁷	× 10 ⁹
0.00	-	0.985	-	-	-	-	-	0.985	-	-	-	-
0.50	0.0076	1.027	27.28	4.21	7.59	1.25	0.0070	1.039	69.35	8.05	14.87	1.25
1.00	0.0070	1.042	86.97	8.07	7.60	1.25	0.0142	1.052	204.43	19.55	14.99	1.25
2.00	0.0070	1.055	326.70	16.84	7.62	1.25	0.0142	1.068	702.31	34.66	15.11	1.25
3.00	0.0142	1.069	30.51	24.14	7.80	1.25	0.0142	1.078	1510.04	50.03	15.22	1.25
4.00	0.0142	1.076	1308.42	32.55	7.90	1.25	0.0215	1.085	2635.19	65.65	15.37	1.25
5.00	0.0215	1.082	2066.87	41.21	8.03	1.25	0.0215	1.088	3317.00	66.16	15.49	1.25
6.00	0.0289	1.086	3013.37	50.11	8.15	1.25	0.0289	1.095	5867.68	97.64	15.74	1.25
8.00	0.0289	1.094	5502.16	68.69	8.28	1.25	0.0365	1.102	10460.13	130.64	15.99	1.25
10.00	0.0365	1.100	8831.59	88.25	85.53	1.25	0.0442	1.10	16470.25	164.61	16.1	1.25
20.00	0.0365	1.119	40240.16	201.16	9.28	1.25	0.0442	1.12	69918.58	349.54	17.60	1.25
30.00	0.0442	1.131	101683.91	338.92	10.04	1.25	0.0442	1.03	167904.92	559.65	18.80	1.25

^a F_{ij} [X, Y] values of other systems can be obtained on request.

Table 2. Stability constants of [Zn-antibiotics-vitamin-B₁] system
 $\mu = 1.0 M NaClO_4, pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01, T = 298 K$

Ligands	log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}^a	log β_{20}^a	log β_{30}^a	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Neomycin	-	-	3.60	6.51	9.10	3.90	7.23	9.46
Chlortetracycline	-	-	4.40	7.61	9.50	4.72	7.93	9.76
Oxytetracycline	-	-	4.50	7.81	9.86	4.83	-	10.20
Tetracycline	-	-	4.80	8.01	9.91	5.13	8.56	10.43
Penicillin-V	-	-	4.91	-	10.00	5.25	8.76	-
Penicillin-G	-	-	4.96	8.12	10.10	5.31	8.83	10.68
Vitamin-B ₁	2.20 (2.34)	3.30 (3.82) ^a	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aA. K. Jain and F. Khan, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1999, 77, 1.

(Studied these complexes at pH 8.50 but the present study has been done at pH 7.30 for values comparison).

bond formation with Zn. The greater stability of penicillin-G than that of penicillin-V complexes is due to the presence of electronegative O in the later than in the former as a result of which, the penicillin-V complexes has more steric hindrance than penicillin-G³.

In case of vitamin-B₁, it is the pyrimidine N that might take part in bond formation with Zn. The structures of

complexes were given in Fig. 1. The values of stability constants of complexes varied from 2.20 to 10.68 which are quite reasonable values therefore, either vitamin-B₁ or antibiotics alone or in combination or in the form of complexes could be used against Zn toxicity⁴.

The values of kinetic parameters have great importance in electrode kinetics. In case of [Zn-neomycin-vitamin-

*(Similar bonding of vitamin - B₁ is with other ligands)

Fig. 1

Note

B₁] system, the values of rate constant k varied from 3.37×10^{-3} to $7.75 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ confirmed the quasireversible nature of electrode processes. Similar values of the order of $10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ were also obtained in case of other systems. The values of transfer coefficient (α) were about 0.50 for all the systems. The values of degree of irreversibility and diffusion coefficient are in accordance with the electrode processes⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water ($4.50 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mho}$). The purity of antibiotics (Aldrich) varied from 90 to 97% and the vitamin-B₁ is 96% pure. The metal, NaClO₄ and HClO₄ solutions were prepared by dissolving the required amount in conductivity water. Requisite amounts of neomycin trisulfate, trihydride, hydrochlorides of all the tetracycline and sodium salts of penicillins were used to prepare their stock solutions. Vitamin-B₁ hydrochloride was used to prepare its solution in conductivity water. The test solution was deaerated by passing pure nitrogen gas before the experiment. pH of the analyte was measured on an Elico digital pH meter (model LI-120). The current-voltage curves were recorded

on a Polarographic Analyzer (Elico CL-362). Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added in the analyte to stabilize its pH at 7.30. 0.001% Triton-X 100 was used as a suppressor.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. P. J. Gellings, *Z. Electrochem. Ber Bun Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 477, 481, 799; 1963, **67**, 167; W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4999.
2. R. Tamamushi and M. Tanaka, *Z. Physik. Chem. New Folge*, 1963, **39**, 117; F. Khan and L. Tantuvay, *Trans. SAEST*, 2000, **35**, 79.
3. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, **3**, 513; J. M. Desiqueria, S. Carvalho, E. B. Paniago, L. Tosi and H. Beraldo, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1994, **83**, 291; B. P. Chakrawarti, A. Tiwari and H. N. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 200.
4. M. D. Walker and D. R. William, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 1186.
5. R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem. New Folge*, 1962, **35**, 211; S. Vajhallya and F. Khan, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1999, **72**, 397.